

**SELF-CONCEPT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF KENDRIYA
VIDYALAYA AND MISSIONARY SCHOOL STUDENTS**

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Abstract:

This paper is trying to highlight the status of self-concept and Academic Achievement Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary school students. Among the students, generally, self-concept is playing very pivotal role. The self-concept is what the individual think of as, his actual self. The part of the environment in which he is involved is known as his 'phenomenal self' and the rest of the environment of which he is aware or to which eh responds is called 'phenomenal environment'. It is said that some variable is definitely effect on self-concept. Academic achievement is played main role for maintaining self-concept. Zimmerman (1979) and Ringle (1981) found that, to the degree that academic success depends on persistent effort and self-confidence are, however, at some point they have to be supplemented by effective cognitive skills. So, in the both schools the teachers should identify the reasons of low academic achievement and implement activities or program for improving children's self-concept.

Key Words: Self-concept, Academic Achievement.

Introduction:

Education is the manifestation of the perfection already in man. This perfection has to be realized and manifested in one's own life. So, self-actualization or realization is most important phenomena in life of an individual. An individual's self-concept includes awareness of what the individual is a how the individual will perform and achieve. In day to day life,. Individual asks number of questions, which are directly or indirectly, related to their 'I' i.e. self. In Hinduism, we know it as 'atma' well known for its individuality, the integration force of once personality and component for the universal cosmos, Brahma.

The self-concept consists of organized conceptual patterns of the 'I' and the 'Me' together value attached to these concepts. Self-concept includes only those perceptions, which are vital, central, personal and important to him/her. Therefore, a self-concept is

dominant element in personality pattern. Larned and Muller (1979) found through cross sectional study that there is positive relationship of self-concept with four areas-physical maturity, peer relation, academic success and adaptiveness to school. Anxiety also plays a crucial role because all of us are victim of anxiety in different ways. A person who suffers from anxiety may not be able to devote his full energy in the performance of a task. Therefore anxiety interferes with the activity and so leaning is impeded. This notion is based on an erroneous understanding to the role of anxiety. It is difficult question to answer as how much anxiety is created for it the anxiety is too much. It would be created a need to avoid the teaching situation and too little anxiety would result in a lack of attention.

Academic Academic achievement is of paramount importance particularly in the present socio-economic and cultural context. David MacClelland (1961) believes that is the course of development individuals acquires a need for Academic achievement. Our present education system is mainly based on competition which is reflected in almost every aspects of it. Right from the stage of admission to nursery class up to the highest level students have to complete with their fellow students. Too much competition in education tends to snatch away childhood from children and youth from the young adolescents. Here we have seen that self-concept and have great influence of scholastic Academic achievement. Therefore teachers should take care of these two factors by providing appropriate environment in the classroom. In India every educational policy emphasizes on the good and proper educational environment. For that purpose government opened schools like Kendriya Vidhyalaya and Navodaya Vidyalaya which provides good environment and quality education for children. Therefore this is an effort to analyses self-concept and Academic achievement of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools.

Objectives:

1. To assess status of self-concept and Academic achievement of KendriyaVidyalaya students.
2. To assess Status of self-concept and Academic achievement of Missionary Schools students.
3. To assess difference in self-concept and Academic achievement between students of KendriyaVidyalya and missionary schools.
4. To assess sex difference with respect to self-concept and Academic achievement of KendriyaVidyalayas students.

5. To find out sex difference with respect to self-concept and Academic achievement of Missionary Schools students.
6. To find out correlation between self-concept and Academic achievement of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary Schools students.

Hypotheses:

1. There will be no significant difference in self-concept and academic achievement between students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools.
2. There will be no significant sex difference with respect to self-concept and academic achievement of Kendriya Vidyalaya Students.
3. There will be no significant sex difference with respect to self-concept and academic achievement of Missionary School Students.
4. There will be no significant correlation between self-concept and Academic achievement of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary Schools students.

Design:-

For this study survey design was used to find out the status of self-concept and academic achievement of students of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary Schools.

Sample:

Sample of the study was comprised of 315 students of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary Schools Bhopal city (KV- 146 and Missionary- 169)

Tools of Data collection:

Data concerning self-concept of students was collected by administering

1. Self-Concept scale of Dr. Harmohan Singh and Saraswati Singh the scale where administered on groups of students of class VII of 4 Kendriya Vidyalayas and 4 Missionary Schools.
2. For academic achievement, half yearly result of class VII was collected from school record for each student.

Analysis and Interpretation of data:

The maximum and minimum scores of self-concept and academic achievement, a classification was calculated and based on equal range, the scores were classified into high, moderate and low.

1. Analysis of the status of self-concept and achievement of Kendriya Vidyalaya.

The mean scores of self-concept and achievement of students were obtained and identified as high, moderate and low based on the above classification and presented in table- 1

Table No. 1. Mean scores and status of self-concept and achievement of students of Kendriya Vidyalayas.

Sr. No	Variables	Mean and Status
1.	Self-concept	84.32
2.	English	57.55
3.	Hindi	58.18
4.	Sanskrit	57.08
5.	Mathematics	42.33
6.	Science	48.47
7.	Social Science	53.02
	Total Achievement	312.15

This table indicates that the status of self-concept is average and moderate and the students of KendriyaVidyalayas achieved better in Hindi than other subjects. May be Hindi is the primary language of KendriyaVidyalayas. The above result may be attributed to environment of the school as well as to lack attention of towards their students in kendriya vidyalaya.

1. Analysis of the status of self-concept and achievement of students of Missionary Schools

The mean scores of self-concept and achievement of students of Missionary Schools are presented in Table-2

Table No. 2. Mean scores and status of self-concept and achievement of students of Missionary Schools.

Sr. No	Variables	Mean and Status
1.	Self-concept	82.69
2.	English	58.97
3.	Hindi	64.79
4.	Sanskrit	60.79
5.	Mathematics	55.23
6.	Science	59.00
7.	Social Science	62.20
	Total Achievement	361.82

It is indicated that missionary schools students have moderate status with respect to self-concept and achieved best in Hindi.

1. Analysis of difference in self-concept and total achievement between KENDRIYA VIDYALAYAS and Missionary students.

To compare self-concept, and achievement of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary Schools students the mean, SD and t- value were computed and result were shown in table 3, and 4.

Table - 3 Mean, SD and t- Value for the scores of Self-concept of students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools.

Variable	Kendriya Vidyalaya (N- 146)		Missionary School (N- 169)		t- value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self-concept	84.32	10.51	82.69	8.69	1.489

Table- 3 indicates that students of KENDRIYA VIDYALAYAS are better than that of Missionary schools students with respect of self-concept. But there is no significant difference between mean scores of self-concept of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary Schools students, The obtained t-value 1.489 is less than the table value 1.97 at 0.005 level of significance for 313 degree of freedom. This result may be due to intake of students of similar background and socio-economics status.

Table – 4 Mean, SD and t- Value for the scores of total academic achievement of students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools.

Variables	Kendriya Vidyalayas (N- 146)		Missionary Schools (N-169)		t-value
	Mean	S D	Mean	S D	
English	57.55	17.31	58.97	14.14	0.799
Hindi	58.18	18.01	64.79	16.33	3.411**
Sanskrit	57.08	17.73	60.64	19.43	1.693
Maths	42.33	23.80	55.23	19.50	5.286**

Science	48.47	20.63	59.00	19.93	4.610**
Social Science	53.02	45.76	62.20	23.63	2.279**
Total Achievement	312.15	97.03	361.82	95.32	4.574**

This table indicates the difference between the mean scores of the achievement in different subjects for Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary School's students. The result indicates that there is a significant difference between mean scores of total achievement of Kendriya Vidyalayas and Missionary School's students. Missionary school students are better than that of Kendriya vidyalaya students with respect to total achievement. The obtained t-value 4.574 is more than the table value 2.59 at 0.01 level of significance for 313 degree of freedom. Therefore the difference is statistically significant.

While the results with respect to the entire subject that missionary schools are better than kendriya vidyalayas. In case of Hindi, Mathematics and Science result is significant at 0.01 level and for social science it is significant at 0.05 level. The above result may be due to result oriented effort of the missionary schools, where may be they emphasis more on the practices, numeration etc.

1. Analysis of sex difference in self-concept, and achievement of Kendriya Vidyalaya Students.

To compare self-concept, and achievement of boys and girls of Kendriya Vidyalayas- the mean, SD, t-value were computed and shown in table -5.

Table No. 6. Mean, SD, t-value for the scores of self-concept, and total achievement of boys and girls of Kendriya Vidyalayas.

	Boys	Girls	
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Variables	N- 79		N-67		t- value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self-concept	81.30	10.48	87.87	9.46	3.941**
Achievement	293.72	100.93	333.88	88.10	2.538**

Table No. 6 shows that there is significant difference between boys and girls with respect to self-concept and total achievement of Kendriya Vidyalaya. Therefore in case of self-concept, girls are better than boys. The result may be attributed to over confidence of boys and sincerity and effort of girls of Kendriya Vidyalaya. It also focuses on equal opportunity give both the sexes in Kendriya Vidyalaya.

1. Analysis of sex difference in self-concept and total achievement of Missionary School Students.

To compare the self-concept and total achievement of boys and girls of Missionary School mean, SD, and t-value where computed and result are shown in table -7

Table No. 6. Mean, SD, t-value for the scores of self-concept and total achievement of boys and girl of Missionary Schools.

Variables	Boys N- 64		Girls N-105		t- value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self-concept	84.50	8.64	81.58	8.91	2.090*
Academic Achievement	366.88	99.06	358.74	93.32	0.537

*Significant at 0.05 level.

Table No. 7 indicates sex difference of Missionary Schools students with respect of self-concept and total achievement. This result indicates that there is significant sex difference in self-concept of missionary school, but there is no significant difference in boys and girls of missionary schools with respect to Academic achievement. The result of superiority of boys in self-concept and in missionary schools may be due to gender bias.

1. Analysis of sex difference in self-concept and total achievement of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools together.

To compare self-concept and total achievement of boys and girls of the schools, the mean, SD, and t-value were computed and presented in table- 8

Variables	Boys (N- 143)		Girls (N-172)		t- value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Self-concept	82.73	9.27	84.03	9.61	1.181
Achievement	326.46	106.21	349.06	91.87	2.024*

*Significant at 0.05 level.

It shows that there is no significant sex difference in self-concept of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary School together but, there is significant difference in total achievement. Since both the schools follow CBSC syllabus, present result may be due to effort and sincerity of girls.

1. Analysis of relationship between self-concept and achievement of students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools.

To find out the interrelationship between self-concept, academic anxiety and achievement the correlation were computed and result were shown in table-9

Table 9: Mean, SD, and t-value for the scores of self-concept, academic anxiety and total achievement the correlation were computed and the results were shown in table- 9

Variables	Self-concept	Total Achievement
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Self-concept	1.000	0.226**
Total Achievement		1.000

**Significant at 0.01 level

Table 9 shows significant positive low correlation between self-concept total achievement of students of Kendriya Vidyalaya Students and Missionary Schools together.

1. Analysis of relationship of self-concept with languages (English, Hindi, Sanskrit) of students of Kendriya Vidyalaya.

Relationship between self-concept, and languages (English, Hindi, Sanskrit) in Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools together

Table -10 Inter correlations between self-concept, academic anxiety and languages (English, Hindi, and Sanskrit) in Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools together

Variables	English	Hindi	Sanskrit
Self-concept	.202**	.093	.156**

*Significant at 0.005 level

**Significant

at 0.005 level

Table- 10 reveals that there is significant positive and low correlation between self-concept and English & Sanskrit. Therefore those students who have higher self-concept than their achievement are better in English and Sanskrit. Hindi is mother tongue of many students that's why neither self-concept nor anxiety effects its achievement much.

1. Analysis of relationship of self-concept with the other subjects (Math, Science, and Social Science) for the students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools together.

To find out the relationship between self-concept and in other subjects (Math, Science, Social Science) correlation were computed and the result shown in table no- 11

Table:- 11 Table -10 Inter correlations between self-concept, and in other subjects (Math, Science, Social Science) in Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools together

Variables	Maths	Sciences	Social Science
Self-concept	.212**	.218*	.196**

*Significant at 0.005 level
 at 0.005 level

**Significant

Table – 11 indicates that there is significant correlation between self-concept and other subjects i.e. mathematics, sciences, and social sciences.

Conclusion and Discussion:

1. Self-concept of the students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary Schools is in average. Therefore, self-concept is dominant element in personality patterns and the knowledge of self-concept is very important in the learning process. The self-concept is a universal idea that can be found in all primitive philosophies and religion.
2. Total achievement of students of Missionary Schools is better than the students of Kendriya Vidyalaya. Academic achievement is ultimately success in the students at school level. May be the various use of different type of programs related to subjects helpful for improving total achievement.
3. Achievement of Missionary School's students in Hindi, English and Sanskrit is better than that of the students of Kendriya Vidyalaya. Achievement of Missionary School's students in Math, Science, Social Science is better than that of the students of Kendriya Vidyalaya.
4. Students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary School possess same level of self-concept. Roger (1941) equates the self-concept with self-structure when he says, the self-concept as the structure may be thought of is an organized configuration of perceptions of the self which are admissible to awareness. It is compared to the perceptions of one's characteristics and abilities, the percepts and concepts of the self in relation to others and to the environment and to the value qualities.
5. Students of Kendriya Vidyalaya and Missionary School differ significantly with respect to their achievement in different subjects. Missionary Schools are better than

Kendriya Vidyalaya with respect to achievement in different subjects. Shivappa (1980) and Burwani (1991) shown in their studies that the achievement in subjects like mathematics and English is some how low. The reason of the low achievement may be generally due to the high lack of self-concept.

6. In case of Kendriya Vidyalaya, the self-concept of girls is better than that of boys while in the case of Missionary School boys are better than girls in self-concept. For Kendriya Vidyalaya, Girls are better than boys in achievement while the considerations of Missionary School's boys are better than girls in total achievement.
7. There is exist positive correlation between self-concept and total achievement. Shah (1978) investigated the same work and found that the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement was significantly positive and linear.

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